

International Student Projects and Sustainable Development Goals: A Perfect Match

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Abstract

Engineering Education is currently going through a transformation, driven by the need for educating better engineers and more engineers, and largely build on elements such as problem orientation, interdisciplinarity, internationalization, digitalization and sustainability. In 2020, the Erasmus+ Strategic Partnership EPIC (Improving Employability Through Internationalization and Collaboration) has combined all these elements, and demonstrated how international and interdisciplinary student projects, focusing on solving real-world problems related to sustainability, can be carried out in a setting where students mainly work together online. A total of 56 students from 7 EU and 2 international universities, with backgrounds ranging from Electrical Engineering and Mechanical Engineering to Textile Technologies and Business Informatics were working on 9 different projects throughout the spring of 2020. The paper presents the experiences from the setup and discusses some general recommendations for setting up this type of projects. The paper goes through the stages of defining and carrying out the projects: Defining the overall framework, identifying problems/project proposals in collaboration with relevant stakeholders, identifying the students and assigning students to projects, preparing students and supervisors, organising the physical kick-off seminar, and supporting the online collaboration. We also discuss evaluation and hand-over of the solutions, to ensure the projects have a lasting impact. We conclude that the sustainable development goals provide a highly motivating framework for interdisciplinary, international student projects based on problem-based learning. We also note that a careful design and execution of the all the preparatory stages are crucial in order for the projects to succeed, and discuss specific recommendations for these.

Keywords: Active Learning; Engineering Education; Conference Information; Project Approaches.

1 Introduction

The engineering professionals we educate today need to master not only their own specific discipline: They have to be able to work in teams, solve problems in collaboration with other people from all over the world and with different backgrounds, and of course also to master digital technologies (Hadgraft & Kolmos, 2020). Recently there has been also a movement towards including sustainability in the curricula: Partly because many of the challenges engineers are working with are related to sustainability, and partly because the focus on sustainability can help in attracting more students to the engineering disciplines. See e.g. (Guerra, 2017) and (Dahms, Krogh Hansen & Otrell-Cass, 2012). It is also well known that Problem-Based Learning (Graaff & Kolmos, 2003) and learning based on projects is a good way for the students to work in interdisciplinary teams and on real-world problems, achieving competences within e.g. project management and communication (Lima, Dinis-Carvalho, Flores & Hattum-Janssen, 2007).

The Erasmus+ EPIC project runs through 2017-2020, each spring semester testing out new ways of setting up international and interdisciplinary student projects with focus on solving real-life problems posed by companies or communities. The students come from one of the eight partner universities (Riga Technical University (Latvia), Technical University of Hamburg (Germany), UPC Barcelona (Spain), University of Stavanger (Norway), UTP University of Life Sciences (Poland), Saxion University of Applied Sciences (The Netherlands), Abdullah Gul University (Turkey) and Aalborg University (Denmark)), and in addition to the universities the project consortium also includes two companies. However, most of the student projects are done in collaboration with companies outside of the formal project partnership. The project work is based on blended mobilities, where the students collaborate mainly online, along with one physical seminar to kick-off the projects. In the first two years (2018 and 2019) the students also had the chance for a second physical meeting,

but in 2020 this was cancelled due to the Covid-19 situation. The project and the previous experiences are described in (Pedersen, Kirikova, Kuladinithi & Janssen, 2019) and (Pedersen & Jensen, 2018). It is a guiding principle throughout the EPIC project that all students work in collaborative projects, yet under the rules and frameworks of their local universities: This also means that students hand in their projects to their home universities and are examined according to their rules and guidelines. This choice is made in order to ensure that the approach is scalable, and that it can be replicated beyond the EPIC consortium without the need for hand-held solutions. Moreover, it makes it possible to overcome some of the more bureaucratic issues in terms of enrolment, recognition, credits etc. On the other hand, this also requires a careful project design to ensure that the students can collaborate and yet fulfil the requirements and learning objectives from their home universities. EPIC is co-funded by the Erasmus+ programme of the European Union, which made it possible for the students to participate free of charge.

One of the challenges in the previous years was to create a common denominator for the different student projects. In 2020, we sought to achieve this by creating a common theme for all the projects: The UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) (UN Development Goals website, 2020). In addition to creating a joint reference framework and demonstrating how the students were all contributing to solving a bigger societal challenge, this also made it possible to experiment with how sustainability can be integrated in many different engineering disciplines.

Our experience and approach are described in this paper. Our main contribution is the walk-through of the whole process from idea to carrying out the projects, with particular focus on sustainability and the SDGs. The paper is organised as follows. First in Section 2, a background for the project is given. After this, we describe the process of integrating sustainability with the student projects, followed by a discussion on our experience and at last the conclusion.

2 Background

As mentioned in the introduction, the EPIC project aims at bringing together students from different disciplines and countries to work together on solving real-world problems defined by companies or other organisations. The model is inspired by the Problem Based Learning model from Aalborg University (Kolmos, Fink & Krogh, 2004), but also largely based on previous Erasmus+ Projects such as COLIBRI (Collaboration and Innovation for Better, Personalized and IT-supported Learning) (COLIBRI website, 2020), where experiences and evaluations demonstrated a high learning outcome for the participating students working on interdisciplinary problems in international groups based on blended learning. However, a main difference is that EPIC is not a particular course, but rather an integration of activities at the partner institutions.

From a student point of view, the semester is organised as illustrated in Figure 1. As it can be seen, there is quite some flexibility in the schedule to accommodate for the different timings at the different universities. Some of the deadlines (e.g. the deadline for handing in the joint report) can also be made flexible if all students have later local project hand-in deadlines.

Figure 1: Semester structure of EPIC

3 Integration of projects and SDGs

In this section, we go through the stages of the EPIC semester: Setting up the projects including defining the projects and the groups, the kick-off seminar, the virtual collaboration phase, and the project hand-over at the end. The main focus throughout the description is on the sustainability aspects and integration of SDGs.

3.1 Setting up the projects

From the beginning, it was decided to use the SDGs as the common frame for the projects. Where in previous years, the focus was on a number of “topics” or “themes” this year it would be an array of problems related to the SDGs. In particular, the following SDGs were chosen (UN Development Goals website, 2020):

- Affordable and Clean Energy (SDG 7)
- Sustainable Cities and Communities (SDG 11)
- Digitalization/Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure (SDG 9)
- Good Health and Well-being (SDG 3)

These areas were decided by the partners during a meeting in September 2019, and would form the framework for the project proposals, which were defined in the next step. The topics were found to be a good fit with the study areas involved and with the companies interested so far. Also, focusing on four of the 17 SDGs would help to make it easier to see the connections between the different projects. Each university was responsible for reaching out to potential company partners in order to define the precise project proposals based on these SDGs. Thus, the project proposals were then defined in collaboration between partner universities and companies, and each of these project proposals would aim on answering one or more of the chosen SDGs, in a way that would also be relevant for the company or companies. The project proposals were defined during October 2019, and ended up with the following nine projects (the number in parenthesis indicate which SDG(s) are covered):

- Digitalisation in manufacturing (RAMBASE) (9)
- Global Recruitment Tool (9,11)
- Secure infrastructure and cyber security challenges (9)
- Measuring carbon footprint for companies (11)
- Energy optimization in 5G (7,9,11)
- Circular textile platform (11)
- Mobile education for waste pickers (3)
- IoT in selective garbage collection (3,11)
- River waste plastics recovery (11)

As the next step, the projects were announced and the students had to apply for participation which is a bit tricky: First of all, the students will not be working on the projects until the spring semester (usually starting around February 1 – for some a bit earlier, for some a bit later), and for some students electives are chosen according to specific schedules at their home universities and participation in EPIC cannot be confirmed until also other priorities are known. Second, there are also constraints from EPIC, i.e. that all projects should have students from at least two countries – and preferably at least four students per project. To solve this challenge, the students had to select their projects before November 30, and in case some projects had not enough students they would have the chance to make another choice. Generally, there was no upper limit on the number of students on each project, but in practice, having more than 8-9 students would imply that the project would be split into multiple sub-projects. Initially, there were allocated four seats per university (due to the limited funding for travelling), but eventually more students were allowed to join so we ended up with 41 students from the eight partner universities. Due to the different timings at the different universities, it was not quite possible to receive all applications by November 30, and despite all good intentions the last students were not added to the list until late January, just two weeks before the joint seminar. Also, eventually not all projects had been filled up, and the partners made an additional (and successful) effort in finding additional students for those projects so that in the end all of the projects had a sufficient number of students. The students were a mix of B.Sc. and M.Sc. students from a variety of disciplines: From engineering, to business, to textile design.

With the focus on SDGs, the project attracted also attention from outside of Europe. Since 2018, Aalborg University and University of Brasilia have been working together on joint student projects on helping create a better life for the thousands of people who worked as waste pickers in the dumpsite of Brasilia – a dumpsite that was closed in 2018, and where several programmes were established to help the waste pickers in the transition to more organised jobs. This case inspired the last three projects on the list, and all of these projects included also students from University of Brasilia who funded their own trip to also participate in the seminar. In this way, the projects could also build on existing collaborations and benefit from being part of more established projects with partners including UNDP (United Nations Development Programme) and the Central Bank of Brazil. With 15 Brazilian students, mainly from Production Engineering, the project ended up with a total of 56 students.

After the groups were formed, the students were connected and onboarded on the communication platform Slack, which was used for communication both for the overall project and within the groups. Also, before the kick-off seminar the students were invited to a Moodle-based platform (Eduspace) to be introduced to the basics of teamwork, project planning and management, and entrepreneurship. This is similar to what was done in the previous years and is not described in further details.

An important part of the preparation phase is also to organise the project supervision. In EPIC, all students have a project supervisor (responsible for the whole project) a local supervisor from their own university, and a company supervisor. All project and local supervisors followed an e-learning course prior to the seminar, and the company supervisors are provided with informative materials about EPIC and work in close dialogue with the project and local supervisors.

3.2 Seminar

The joint seminar is a physical meeting, which was this year held in Hamburg, Germany. It plays a crucial role in all the projects, because the students meet face-to-face: They get to know each other, scope the projects, make an initial problem analysis, and plan the rest of the project time. The experience from previous years, but also from previous projects (Dahms, 1998), stress how important this physical component is in order to the virtual collaboration phase to be successful. In the EPIC project, the seminar was held during a week in February, with five full working days for all participants (students and teachers/supervisors).

In this paper, we will mainly focus on the activities that deal with sustainable development goals. However, to give the full picture it is important to also mention that the week included workshops that would take the students through the initial steps of the project: They would e.g. define the project scope, define the expected contributions of individual students, create a project plan with milestones, and also define success criteria for both the project and the process (e.g. collaboration). Based on previous experience this process was well structured, and throughout the workshops the students would fill out templates to help them ensure that the results would be useful afterwards. This is a balance between giving the students freedom to define their own structures (thus providing ownership) and ensuring that the projects are student-led, and on the other hand to scaffold and steer the process. Based on the experience of previous years, we acknowledge that it is very important for the students to reach good project plans during the seminar – to avoid having to completely redo the plan afterwards in an all-virtual setting where this is much more difficult.

In the previous years, the joint content of the seminar was mainly dealing with the most generic part of the projects, e.g. project management, teamwork, peer assessment methods etc., and it was hard to present and discuss the content parts since all projects were dealing with different problems and themes. The SDGs made it possible to also bind the content closer together, in particular through the following activities:

- Day 1: The introduction to the seminar included an introduction to the UN Sustainable Development Goals. This was in the form of an oral presentation and formed the basis for the initial discussions in the groups about the scoping of the projects.
- Day 2: Keynote presentation by students from KU Leuven, who won a 3.000 km race for solar-powered cars through the Australian outback. The keynote was delivered as an interactive session, where the students discussed and had to make decisions throughout the presentation. The focus was partly on sustainability, but equally on setting out joint project objectives and achieving them as a team.

- Day 3: Keynote presentation by one of the professors from University of Brasilia, who was previously president of the waste management organisation (SLU) of Brasilia, and who led the closure of what was the world's second largest dumpsite (and the largest in Latin America). The talk was focusing on both technical, social and cultural aspects of the transformation, also to demonstrate to the students the importance of understanding the context of the engineering work.

Throughout the week, professors from the different universities were available for discussions with all the groups. In this way, the groups received inputs and feedback from their supervisors as well as from other professors, e.g. on the sustainability topics.

3.3 Virtual collaboration phase

During the virtual collaboration phase, the students were working mainly within the nine projects. The format of the collaboration was varying from group to group, but included elements such as online meetings, shared documents, and feedback on each other's work. Moreover, we created a system for systematically providing peer feedback among the students. The students also received supervision from both EPIC supervisors, local supervisors, and the involved companies.

3.4 Handing over the projects

The main purpose of the student projects is of course the students learning. However, it is also highly motivating for the students to see their results in use – and the process of taking it from “student project” to real-life implementation is an experience with many learning points. While few of the nine projects were finished as final production-ready products by the end of the semester, we see three different ways in which the projects are being used or brought to use:

- Some of the projects end up in prototypes, which are ready to be tested. This is for example the case for the IoT in selective garbage collection project. This project aims at improving the collection of garbage in the city of Brasilia by installing sensors in containers, so it is possible to plan the collection according to the full containers – in particular, this makes it possible to ensure that recyclables end up in the official recycling facilities (where the previous waste pickers are working) rather than being stolen by unofficial pickers. The prototype is limited in the sense that it should be tested at a smaller scale first, and when scaling up more specialised devices should be used.
- Some projects end up in the form of a report with analysis and suggestions, which can be useful for the company/companies involved. This was for example the case for the Energy Optimization in 5G project, where the students came up with findings and recommendations which was supported by analysis and simulations. While the impact here is less tangible, it does have an impact as it provides the companies with insights and ideas that they might not have been able to achieve on their own.
- Some projects develop master thesis which may be useful for companies involved, but this might also be seen as a research work with SDG recommendations beyond the directly involved companies. This is the case with “River waste plastics recovery” where the involved management students write “The Economics Of Plastic Recovery In Rivers: Case of Brasilia”. This work investigates the business case and provides a socioeconomic analysis of plastic recovery from freshwater based on the collaboration with the engineering students in the EPIC group and collaboration with students and professors from Brazil.

For several of the projects, it was initially planned that the handover would include physical visits; For example, a joint seminar between the European and Brazilian students was planned to happen in Brasilia making both implementation and additional field studies possible. Due to the Covid-19 situation this was not possible, and even the possibility for the local students to interact with companies and communities was limited due to the situation. However, it is planned that some of these activities will be resumed if the situation normalises in the near future.

4 Discussion

4.1 Project framing

Compared to the previous years, one of the main differences was that the SDGs was used to link the different projects better together. We noted that in the past it was hard for the students to connect projects across topics (and in some cases even sub-projects within the same topics): For example, two projects on Internet of Things could be very different if one group of students worked on communication aspects, and another group worked on an application. Even if the students were having regular meetings and updating each other on progress, the projects would develop in different directions and it would become harder and harder to benefit from the meetings. Here, we experienced that the SDGs provided a very useful frame: Students could see how they all contributed to solve some of the same problems, even if the solutions were different, which also made it easier to comment and suggest on the works – and because the SDGs made it possible to communicate a joint vision for the projects. This was also supported by the activities during the seminar. However, it seems that the potential in using the framing to link the projects together is even higher, and could be strengthened through preparation materials, more activities during the seminar, and maybe also during more activities throughout the virtual collaboration phase.

We were also positively surprised about the company interests in the SDGs. During this study we did not extend that collaboration to e.g. Non-Governmental Organisations or community organisations (except for some of the collaboration partners in Brazil), but this could be an interesting direction to explore in the future.

4.2 Student evaluations

Each student group documented their work by handing in a joint EPIC report. The report consists of two parts: One part regards the content of the project, and the other part regards the evaluation of the process and reflections on the students learning. When studying the evaluation reports, we found the following comments to be quite consistent:

- The students found it highly motivating to work with the Sustainable Development Goals.
- The students liked to work on projects that can make a social/environmental difference.
- The students appreciated working in international and interdisciplinary environments and found that the groups were working towards a common goal.

On the other hand, the students also indicated some areas of further improvement:

- Supervision from the different supervisors was not always consistent, i.e. different supervisors would have different point of views.
- For some of the projects, the students would like a higher commitment from the involved companies.
- The Covid-19 situation created challenges for some of the students, mainly due to major changes in how other learning activities were carried out/delivered – but also limiting the field work to be carried out in EPIC and making it impossible to carry out the second physical mobility component.

By the end of the project, the students were asked to provide also a quantitative evaluation of the whole EPIC experience. Figure 2 presents the overall evaluation of the personal experience, and demonstrates that the students overall were happy with the experience. They found that the work will be helpful for them in their future education/career, and that it has made them better prepared for both the national and international labor markets.

Figure 2: Students overall evaluation of EPIC on a scale 1-5, where 1="Not at all" and 5="Very much".

Figure 3 presents the students evaluation of how the methods used in EPIC contributes to improving the learning offer. While the evaluations are generally positive, it is noted that especially the promotion of active learning and problem-based learning receives high scores along with the skills within problem solving, collaboration, entrepreneurship, creativity and innovation. As such, we believe that the approach is useful in order to help the students achieve important skills for their studies and careers.

Figure 3: Students evaluation of to what extent the teaching methods of EPIC supports the listed objectives on a scale 1-5, where 1="Not at all" and 5="Very much".

Note that two of the questions to the students were further elaborated in the electronic questionnaire they filled out. Question 1: "Increasing employability through closer collaboration between students and industry, by promoting active and problem-based learning and international collaboration", Question 2: "Increasing the labor market relevance of education through closer collaboration between industry and academia, and making the students better prepared for both national and international labour markets".

4.3 Project handover

The vision of "making a difference" is a main motivational factor for the students and ending up with a solution that is actually being used is something many of the students would like to achieve.

However, making a real impact requires that:

- The projects can be either fully handed over to e.g. companies or communities who can keep using and maintaining the products without further help from the students – or they can be handed over to

new groups of students who will continue the development. In both cases, the projects need to be quite mature and well documented – something that is not often the focus when doing proof-of-concept developments.

- The projects are quite complete – to fit with the timeframe/workload of the students as well as the learning objectives in curricula the projects are often scoped to cover only limited parts of the full problem. This makes it hard for other organisations to use the projects, unless they have the resources to complete the missing parts.

Overcoming these challenges requires among other things a project scope that fits well with the learning objectives of the students, together with a problem that fits the time/workload available for the students, or as it was the case in some of our projects that the students are willing to spend some of their spare time to bring the projects to a more final stage.

On this, we also note that curricula and learning objectives do not always reward students for making the products “production ready”, including thorough documentation and hand-over processes. This implies that the students can be caught in a lack of alignment between learning objectives, assessments and this part of the learning objectives (Biggs & Tang, 2011) – thus creating a dilemma for the students of prioritizing maximizing the project outcome/impact and the grade achieved. We would encourage universities and educators to consider this when integrating sustainability into the learning objectives of engineering studies.

5 Conclusion

Our experience demonstrates that the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) fit well with international and student projects, which aim at bringing students from different backgrounds and disciplines together to work on solving real-world problems. In particular, the SDGs provide a strong framework for binding the projects together and show the students that they work towards a common goal – even if they work on different projects or sub-projects, and even if they work on projects that are different in terms of technical content. With the high motivational factor, we also believe this indicates that working on sustainability can help in attracting more students to engineering in the future. On the other hand, we also found that it is important to:

- Align learning objectives and assessment with both interdisciplinary project work and sustainability, so that the sustainability is integrated in the curricula and not just a toning of existing learning activities.
- Work closely with stakeholders, scoping the projects carefully, and maybe adjusting the learning objectives to include e.g. handover processes, so that at least some of the projects can end up being actually used and creating an impact.
- Prepare both students and supervisors on working with sustainability, and to not only consider sustainability from a technical point of view but also including social, cultural and economic aspects.

Our case involved 56 students from 9 different universities in 9 different countries. We hope that in the future more universities will integrate sustainability into their curricula at a larger scale, keeping in mind the importance of aligning learning objectives, assessments and learning activities, and that this will make it possible to conduct more systematic and larger studies.

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